

UNDERSTANDING THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN LANGUAGE, SPEECH, AND POLITENESS IN HUMAN INTERACTION

Sarimsakova Shoira Ulug'bek qizi

PhD student of National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400304>

Annotation: Language, as a multifaceted medium of communication, intertwines with speech patterns and politeness strategies to facilitate effective human interaction. This article analyzes the intricate relationship between language, speech, and politeness, exploring their dynamic interplay in shaping social exchanges and fostering harmonious communication. The relationship between politeness, language and speech is a complex and culturally influenced aspect of communication. Politeness in language refers to the use of linguistic strategies to mitigate potential face-threatening acts and maintain social harmony. It involves expressing consideration for the feelings, desires, and social expectations of others. The study of politeness is often associated with the field of pragmatics, which examines how context influences the interpretation of meaning in communication.

Key words: speech, language, politeness, honorifics, pitch, volume, nonverbal clause, culture

Language has a complex role in politeness, and its subtleties greatly influence how people interact with one another. Language is the medium through which complex politeness methods are expressed; these strategies are based on a variety of complex linguistic mechanisms. These include the sensitive use of honorifics, the deft use of markers of politeness, and the subtle adjustment of formality levels. These decisions are more than just language; they have a profound emotional impact, expressing reverence, respect, and subtly expressing social position in the context of conversation. Moreover, these language cues are not separate from cultural norms and societal expectations; rather, they are deeply entwined. They are profoundly ingrained in a language community's collective psyche and are not just arbitrary linguistic constructions. The variety of politeness strategies used in a particular linguistic environment is greatly shaped and influenced by these ingrained norms and expectations, which gently advise people on appropriate forms of polite communication. For example, In English culture, polite communication often involves the use of phrases like "please," "thank you," and addressing people with titles like "Mr.," "Mrs.," or "Ms." In Uzbek culture, showing respect through greetings, such as using formal titles like "Ustoz" (teacher) or "Aka" (elder brother), and offering

hospitality like serving tea or sweets, are typical politeness strategies within their societal norms. Both cultures have ingrained customs that guide individuals on how to communicate courteously within their respective linguistic environments.

Speech, an intricate blend of tone, pitch, volume, and non-verbal cues, functions as a vital complement to language when expressing politeness. Beyond words alone, paralinguistic features intricately intertwine, including the subtle nuances of intonation patterns, purposeful gestures, and nuanced body language. These elements significantly enhance the communicative intent of language, deeply impacting how politeness is perceived within an utterance. The modulation and deliberate alteration of speech patterns assume a pivotal role in signifying politeness, underscoring the paramount significance of context and the intricate cultural subtleties that underpin our comprehension of politeness within speech. As an illustration, in English culture, altering speech patterns can signify politeness. For instance, using a softer tone or adding phrases like “if you don’t mind” or “could you please” are ways to convey politeness, emphasizing respect and consideration in communication while within Uzbek culture, adjusting speech patterns to convey politeness extends to expressing gratitude. Saying “Rahmat” (thank you) or “Rahmat, agar imkon bo’lsa” (thank you, if possible) demonstrates appreciation while acknowledging the other person’s potential inconvenience, reflecting the cultural value placed on courteous communication. Furthermore, showing politeness in speech may involve using phrases like “Sog’ bo’ling” (be well) or “Qadr-qimmatigizni bilib olganman” (I recognize your worth) to convey good wishes or express respect. These phrases emphasize consideration and acknowledgment of the other person’s well-being or importance. Politeness in Uzbek communication might also encompass using indirect language to avoid causing offense or discomfort. Expressions like “Uzur so’rayman” (I apologize) or “Bir qoshiq qonimdan keching” (Give up a spoon of my blood) are employed to soften requests or conversations, prioritizing harmony in social interactions.

The notion of civility is still closely associated with certain cultural contexts and exhibits significant cultural diversity. The expectations and standards surrounding appropriate language and speech patterns in social interactions vary greatly between distinct cultural environments. In high-context cultures, indirect speech acts are common and polite interactions are governed by subtlety, as contextual clues and implicit communication are highly valued. Here, implicit politeness techniques include deploying subtle gestures or

ambiguous language gently express respect and preserve harmony in communication. On the other hand, directness and explicitness are valued more highly in low-context societies. Sincerity and directness are admired; they influence how politeness is communicated. Here, courteous communication typically entails the use of unambiguous requests, specific expressions of gratitude, and the avoidance of ambiguity, which reflects a society that places a high importance on accuracy and open communication. These disparate approaches to etiquette underscore the complex nuances ingrained in cultural contexts, influencing and directing the acceptable modes of communication in various communities.

In English-speaking societies, politeness often involves respecting personal boundaries and individual space. For instance, maintaining an appropriate physical distance when conversing, respecting others' privacy, and using polite phrases like "May I interrupt you for a moment?" or "Would you mind if I join you?" showcase consideration for others' comfort and space. For instance, in Uzbek culture, displaying politeness extends to hospitality and gestures of goodwill. Offering tea or refreshments upon someone's arrival, expressing concern for their well-being with phrases like "Salomat bo'ling" (stay healthy) or "Omon bo'ling" (take care), and inviting guests to partake in meals or gatherings reflect the emphasis on warmth and hospitality as integral facets of politeness. Moreover, within both cultures, non-verbal cues significantly contribute to politeness. In English culture, maintaining eye contact, offering a firm handshake, or nodding affirmatively can convey attentiveness and respect during interactions. In Uzbek culture, gestures such as placing a hand over one's heart or lightly touching one's chest while speaking express sincerity, humility, and politeness. These diverse examples highlight how both English and Uzbek cultures embrace multifaceted expressions of politeness, encompassing verbal and non-verbal cues, gestures of hospitality, and respectful behaviors that are deeply ingrained in social interactions, reflecting the values and societal norms unique to each culture.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the interconnection between politeness and the nuances of language and speech is a complex interplay influenced by multifarious factors. Cultural diversity, social dynamics, and contextual intricacies intricately mold the manifestations of politeness within linguistic and speech patterns. Within this intricate web, individuals navigate their interactions by deploying an array of linguistic strategies, each tailored to convey respect, preserve social harmony,

and deftly negotiate the delicate fabric of interpersonal relationships. The deeply ingrained cultural values and societal norms significantly shape the expression of politeness. From the directness and explicitness in low-context cultures, such as English-speaking societies, where explicit verbal acknowledgments of gratitude and clear requests underscore respect, to the high-context cultures like Uzbek, where implicit expressions and subtleties in speech serve as vehicles for maintaining harmony and displaying deference, each culture exhibits its unique tapestry of politeness. Furthermore, individuals within these cultural contexts deftly navigate the intricacies of politeness by skillfully employing non-verbal cues, honorifics, indirect speech acts, and gestures of hospitality. These nuanced linguistic strategies not only convey respect but also act as conduits for building and sustaining meaningful interpersonal relationships within their respective cultural frameworks. Ultimately, the complex relationship between politeness, language, and speech underscores the profound importance of understanding cultural diversity and contextual nuances in effective communication. The ability to navigate these intricate layers of linguistic expression facilitates not only polite discourse but also fosters deeper connections, mutual understanding, and cultural appreciation in the rich tapestry of global interactions.

References:

1. Crystal, D. "A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics." John Wiley & Sons., 2008.-P. 389-295.
 2. Levelt, W. J. M. "Speaking: From Intention to Articulation." MIT Press.,1989.-P.415-418.
 3. Gaskell, G., & Marslen-Wilson, W. D. Integrating form and meaning: A distributed model of speech perception. *Language and Cognitive Processes, 1997 12*(5-6), -P. 613-656.
 4. Pinker, S. "The Language Instinct: How the Mind Creates Language." Harper Perennial Modern Classics.,1994.-P.436-441.
- Sarimsakova, Sh.U. "Politeness in pragmatics." Scientific Progress, V.2, № 6, 2021- P. 1455-1457.
- Sarimsakova, Sh.U. " Verbal and nonverbal politeness" Fan va ta'lim integratsiyalashuvida barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlari. T:2023.-P.108-110.